

NAŠE MORE 2025

4th International Conference of Maritime Science & Technology

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

SVEUČILIŠTE
U DUBROVNIKU
UNIVERSITY
OF DUBROVNIK

Dubrovnik, 18 – 19 September 2023

University of Dubrovnik
Faculty of Maritime Studies

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DECARBONIZATION OF ESTONIAN FERRY LINES – CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

Decarbonization in the shipping industry plays a central role in global research and innovation activities. Ways to achieve zero-emission shipping include energy efficiency improvements, operational changes, the use of non-fossil fuels, retrofit and redesign of ships. Although the environmental regulations of the European Commission and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) apply only to ships above 5000 GT, the local industry representatives and authorities in many European countries also target greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction from a wider shipping sector, including smaller ships and island ferries. To achieve the GHG emissions reductions, low-carbon fuels such as biodiesel, hydrogen, and its derivatives have been proposed for ferries along with direct electrification. From the design and operation viewpoint, these alternatives involve higher investment risk, including (a) capital-intensive infrastructure requirements, (b) powertrain implementation and onboard storage sizing, and (c) fuel availability and price volatility. This study focuses on an Estonian ferry line, which serves as the primary means of transportation for connecting the mainland. Consequently, it plays a critical role in facilitating the mobility of cargo and passengers to and from the islands. We analyse possible future energy system development paths to evaluate potential alternative fuels, based on existing ferries and local port infrastructure. Subsequently, we develop and apply an energy-transport optimization model to analyse alternative fuel investments from a techno-economic- environmental viewpoint. Finally, we present a preliminary comparative analysis of GHG emissions reductions and operating costs from the perspective of energy consumption, supporting the industry's decision makers in evaluating the future competitiveness of the shipping lines.

Keywords: decarbonization, shipping, alternative fuels, electrification

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Commission has adopted the Fit for 55 initiative to align the EU's policies on climate, energy, transport, and taxation with its target of reducing net-zero GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030 [1]. This aligns with the European Green Deal, which aims to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. Estonia's National

Energy and Climate Plan (NECP 2030) sets similar goals, targeting a 70% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 and 80% by 2050, compared to 1990 levels [2].

Currently, IMO and EU GHG regulations focus on ships larger than 5,000 GT, with some rules applying to those over 400 GT. However, FuelEU Maritime [3], coming into effect on January 1, 2025, introduces exemptions for certain vessel categories, including passenger ships operating between islands with fewer than 200,000 inhabitants. Additionally, various vessel types- such as fishing boats, tugs, waterbuses, and pilot boats- are currently excluded from EU decarbonization regulations. Despite being smaller in size, these ships contribute to an estimated 15–20% of total maritime GHG emissions [4], highlighting a substantial regulatory gap.

Efforts are made to incentivize low-carbon fuels and power solutions with GHG intensity limits on energy used on board the ships. Nevertheless, the European Maritime Transport Environmental Report 2025 [5] reveals that the use of alternative fuels and sources of power has increased, despite being still marginal.

Estonia, located in northeastern Europe, has a population of approximately 1.3 million [6] and a coastline of about 3 800 km, nearly six times longer than its mainland border. It includes around 2 200 islands, many of which, especially in western Estonia, are historically and presently dependent on maritime transport.

Saare County, which includes Saaremaa (the largest island in the Baltic Sea) and Muhu (the third largest island in Estonia), has a low population density of 10.9 inhabitants per square kilometer [6]. These islands are primarily accessed by ferry services, with only limited support from aviation. Most passengers and cargo rely on a combination of sea and road transport.

This study focuses on an Estonian ferry line that operates between the mainland (port of Virtsu) and Muhu island (port of Kuivastu). Muhu island is connected to Saaremaa Island with a causeway, making the ferry connection the primary link to the mainland for the population of about 34 000 people [7]. Currently the ferry line has two double-ended ferries: one with conventional diesel engine and the other one with diesel-electric hybrid engine. In this study, we evaluate and assess the following research questions: (1) What is the energy demand for the ferry line under varying weather conditions? (2) Can this line be operated by fully electric plug-in hybrid ferries? (3) What are the GHG emission reductions and fuel operating cost savings if electric or other alternative fuel island ferries are deployed on this line?

The following study comprises of chapters: Methodology, Results and Discussion, Conclusion.

Methodology section describes the currently operating ferries and analyses how the energy-transport optimization model was built. In the subsections also operating costs derived from the fuel consumption and GHG emissions are assessed. The results and discussion chapter brings out the findings of the analyse, including its GHG emission reduction and explains its main shortages. The conclusion chapter summarizes the study and points out the main aspects of continuation and future steps.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. System Description

The ferry route from the port of Virtsu on the mainland to the port of Kuivastu on the island of Muhu, shown in Figure 1 has the length of 3.7 nm, and depending on the season there are up to 30 daily ferry crossings. The time required for a one-way trip, considering the embarkation and disembarkation time of passengers and vehicles, and the time required for loading and unloading the ferry, is under normal weather conditions 35–45 minutes, with the crossing time not exceeding 28 minutes. The electricity grid in the region will be expanded in near future with a new 330 kV connection, enabling the construction of fast charging infrastructure.

Figure 1 Illustration of the ferry route and the related infrastructure. Legend: port (large black circle), town or other node (small black circle), wind turbines (green circle), ferry route (dotted black line), electricity grid (330 kV: light blue line, 110 kV: blue line; existing: solid, planned: dashed), road (dark gray line). [8]

To evaluate the technical feasibility of the alternative fuel investments, the future energy system development paths must be considered. Currently, electricity charging infrastructure does not exist in the ports of Virtsu and Kuivastu. However, the electricity grid is sufficient for the charging infrastructure after the grid expansion. We assume that the electricity can be sourced at the hourly area price, with an additional transmission fee of 2 c/kWh and port operator margin of 2 c/kWh. The hourly area prices are retrieved from ENTSO-E [9]. For hydrogen, no large-scale green hydrogen production plants currently exist in Estonia. The fuel is estimated to be available in larger quantities and lower costs by 2030 through the Nordic Baltic Hydrogen Corridor [10], but would require an additional road transport step. By 2040, local production or potential expansion of the hydrogen transmission network would make the fuel more directly available for the ports located in the mainland [10]. As baseline value, we assume that hydrogen is available in compressed form at a constant price of 10 €/kg.

Biomethane (CBG) as sustainable marine fuel has several advantages with one of them being an alternative to reduce GHG emissions [11]. The evolution and feasibility of biogas across the world is currently uneven. The development depends on the availability of feedstocks but also on the policies that encourage its production and use. Europe is the largest producer of biogas today [12]. According to the European commission, Estonia can replace about 25% of the current natural gas consumption (imports) with biomethane. Currently, 20% of its sustainable biomethane potential is deployed. Beyond its emission reduction potential, biomethane is also an attractive option due to its availability in Estonia, which is also

supported by the rise of production to the target of 100 million m³ by 2035 [13]. Currently, most of the biomethane produced in Estonia is used in the transport sector and there are several filling stations around the country. For biomethane, we assume the baseline price to be 1.25 €/kg [14].

2.2. Ship Modelling

Currently, there are two sister ferries operating on the Virtsu-Kuivastu line. Depending on the season, the timetable for operating varies with less trips per day during winter period and more trips in the summer period. The double-ended sister vessels Piret and Töll, the latter shown in Figure 2, were built in 2017. The newbuilt passenger ferries were using conventional marine diesel oil for operating, and in 2019, the ferry Töll was retro- fit to diesel-electric hybrid. The technical parameters for Töll are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2 Passenger ferry Töll.

Table 1 Technical parameters of the reference ferry Töll.

Parameter LOA [m]	Value 114
BOA [m]	19.7
Draft [m]	4.0
Gross tonnage [t]	4987
Speed [kn]	15
Main engine	2×1520 kW (MTU 16V400M03)
Auxiliary engine	2×1320 kW (MTU 12V4000M33F)
Battery capacity [kWh]	678
Passenger capacity	700
Vehicle capacity	150

To estimate the fuel consumption of the island ferries, data collection was conducted. The actual schedule data for 2024 was retrieved from the ferry operator. For each voyage, the speed profiles were determined based on minute-level AIS data [15]. Available charging time was estimated by subtracting one minute from the time at port due to charging connection and disconnection. The load profile was estimated based on a reported load example [16], which was time-normalised and divided into three sections following [17]: departure, cruising, and arrival. The instantaneous power consumption P_i was calculated using nominal power consumption P_o , operating speed v_i and its nominal value v_o , operating load x_i , scale factor n and overall efficiency η_{tot} , and auxiliary power consumption P_{aux} as follows:

$$P_i = \frac{x_i \cdot P_o \cdot v_i^n}{\eta_{tot}} + P_{aux} \quad (1)$$

For overall efficiency, the conversion losses were estimated based on the power conversion system configuration. This resulted in the following efficiency estimations at nominal load: diesel (MDO) 41%, diesel-electric hybrid 38%, hydrogen (H₂) 46%, biomethane (CBG) 46% and fully electric (EL) 88%. For simplicity, the auxiliary power consumption P_{aux} was estimated to be constant of 200 kW for all the alternative fuels. Finally, the simulated profiles were aggregated on a ten-minute level, maintaining the correct sequence of information whether the ferry is on route or in port.

In actual operations, power consumption varies due to external factors. One of the most significant in Estonian waters is the presence of ice conditions and low ambient temperatures. Ice conditions increase ship resistance depending on ice thickness, while navigation in ice requires slower speeds and more precise manoeuvring. Icebreaking effort, friction and vibration from ice contact, and heating auxiliary systems substantially increase the energy demand under winter conditions. The applied energy consumption calculation method does not adequately account for these factors, highlighting the need for physics-based simulations in further analyses. In this work, we approximate the influence of ice and weather conditions by scaling the calculated energy consumption with three factors: 1.0 for clear, 1.5 for average, and 2.0 for rough.

2.3. GHG Emissions Data

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive methodology which is used in various industry sectors to evaluate the environmental impacts associated with all scopes of a product's life cycle [18]. In maritime industry, this includes energy use and emissions linked to the construction, operating and decommissioning of ships. The EU and the IMO have introduced methodological frameworks [19,20] within the LCA context to support the consistent estimation of Well-to-wake (WtW) GHG emissions. These frameworks are built upon sustainability criteria and GHG emissions reduction targets, aiming to promote the adoption of low-carbon and sustainable alternative fuels on a global scale.

In this study, the theoretical GHG emissions for fuel alternatives are assessed according to the guidelines of FuelEU Maritime [3] by calculating WtW GHG emissions of the LCA. The total GHG emissions include the Well-to-Tank (WtT) emissions of the energy carrier supply and Tank-to-Wake (TtW) emissions of the total fuel use, and can be calculated as:

$$WtW = WtT + TtW \quad (2)$$

and Sweden electricity is produced from renewable sources of energy, whereas for example in Estonia and in Poland, fossil fuels are the main sources [21]. In the case of using fossil sources for electricity generation, electrification and hybridization may not always be carbon-free solution and might potentially produce significant amount of GHG emissions [22]. Due to the non-renewable sources in electricity production in Estonia, in this study the assessment for fully electric and diesel-electric hybrid ships is not assessed by FuelEU Maritime according to which coefficients in WtT and TtW are not applicable. For electricity, the WtW GHG emissions were assessed with equation:

$$WtW = EE \cdot g_{gel} \quad (3)$$

where EE is the total energy demand and g_{gel} is the electricity emission factor. To represent the current grid electricity, the emission factor was estimated to be 417 gCO₂eq/kWh, based on the national electricity production mix in 2024 [23]. A similar method has been used in several earlier studies [24–26]. For an alternative scenario, where the electricity is either (a) primarily sourced from renewable production such as wind power or (b) the production mix in the market area develops and the emission intensity decreases, we considered emission factor equal to the neighbouring market area, i.e. Finland's 32 gCO₂eq/kWh [27].

2.4. Techno-economic Model

The economic feasibility of developed scenarios was studied with a linear cost-optimization program, implemented in Pyomo (version 6.8.2) [28] and solved with CBC (version 2.10.11) [29]. The model simulates the ferry operation at a ten-minute resolution and minimizes the objective function:

$$C_{tot} = \sum_{t=1}^{TT} P_t \cdot c_{MDO} + \eta_{charge} \cdot P_t \cdot c_{ct,el} + c_{grid} \cdot P_t + P_t \cdot c_{H2} + P_t \cdot c_{CBG} + c_{G}$$

which determines the total fuel operating cost C_{tot} from the calculated ten-minute power consumption P_t , fuel cost c , and for the electric configurations, charger efficiency η_{charge} , hourly electricity price $c_{t,el}$, and grid tariff c_{grid} . The alternative fuel configurations were individually simulated with single-parameter sensitivity analysis for on-board fuel storage and, for electric and hybrid-electric ferries, shore charger capacity. The analysis only considers fuel operating costs and excludes capital expenditures for initial investments and component replacements (e.g., battery, fuel cell).

Ferry energy demand was set as a hard constraint, creating an infeasible scenario if the demand was not met for example due to insufficient charging rate or on-board fuel storage capacity. Charging rate limits were imposed for the ferries depending on the alternative fuel: for electricity based on the charger capacity, for biomethane assuming a fast-filling station [30], and for hydrogen assuming shore-to-ship bunkering [31]. Additionally, the on-board fuel storage was initialized at 50% with a cyclic storage constraint, and state-of-charge constraint assumed depending on the alternative fuel: hydrogen 8–100% due to refueling margin [32] and electricity 10–90% to manage battery state-of-health.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Comparison of fuel operating costs

We simulated two representative operational weeks with: a low-demand week with 115 trips and a peak-demand week with 177 trips. To capture operational variability, three energy consumption levels were considered across diesel, fully electric and diesel-electric hybrid scenarios, reflecting the effects of varied ice and weather conditions. For electric and diesel-electric hybrid scenarios, three charger capacities, i.e. 5.0 MW, 2.5 MW and 1.0 MW, were evaluated to account for infrastructure limitations.

Figure 3 presents the estimated reductions in fuel operating costs for the analyzed configurations. In all scenarios, diesel-electric hybrid operation offers cost improvements over diesel. Notably, higher charger capacities enable significantly greater savings, up to 46%, by allowing increased electric operation. However, this benefit diminishes in high-demand scenarios where the operation relies more on diesel. At the lowest charger capacity, hybrid systems even lead to higher costs, that is –5%, due to reduced overall efficiency. Similarly, the fully electric operation is highly dependent on charger capacity. Under the current operating schedules, full electrification is feasible only with the highest charger capacity and is not possible under the high-demand scenario. When feasible, however, fully electric systems provide the greatest cost reductions, i.e. 75–78%, compared to diesel. The small variation is due to higher consumption necessitating charging during more expensive hours. Among indirect electrification options, biomethane and hydrogen are technically feasible across all conditions. Biomethane slightly outperforms the diesel-electric hybrid option, savings being 58%, but in contrast, hydrogen results in a cost increase of 27% relative to diesel, primarily due to the expected high fuel price.

Figure 3 Relative fuel operating cost reduction (%) for different alternative fuel configurations in comparison to diesel-fueled operation for three levels of fuel consumption based on weather conditions clear, average, and rough. Infeasible scenarios are indicated with (x).

3.2. Estimated emissions of alternatives

Figure 4 presents WtW GHG emissions for the simulated period consisting of two representative operational weeks. With diesel, baseline emissions of 139 tCO₂eq are reached. For diesel-electric hybrid configurations, emissions follow the trend of fuel operating costs, depending on charger capacity, which governs the required diesel consumption. With current grid electricity, emissions range from 92 to 141 tCO₂eq; with low-emission electricity, from 37 to 124 tCO₂eq. Similarly, emissions for the fully electric configuration depend on electricity sourcing. With current grid electricity, emissions are 74 tCO₂eq, not significantly lower than for hybrid. However, with low-emission electricity, emissions decrease to 5 tCO₂eq. This represents an optimistic scenario, as Estonia is currently a high-emission electricity market area, and such values are unlikely to be achieved solely through grid electricity in the near term. Hydrogen yields the lowest emissions at 4 tCO₂eq but, as discussed earlier, faces challenges related to fuel availability. The same considerations as for electricity apply, though low emissions are likely due to the required compliance with green hydrogen regulations such as RFNBO [33]. Biomethane also provides a significant reduction, with emissions of 23 tCO₂eq.

Figure 4 WtW GHG emissions for different alternative fuel configurations in average weather conditions with two alternative options for electricity sourcing. Infeasible scenarios are indicated with (x).

4. CONCLUSION

Battery-electric propulsion systems are gaining increasing attention in various maritime applications due to benefits including low airborne and underwater noise, reduced vibration and low-emission operation. From the perspective of fuel operating costs and GHG emissions, fully electric island ferries appear to be promising option for the studied Estonian route and warrant further investigation. Among the alternative fuels, biomethane offers a more practical option than hydrogen for hybrid configurations due to its availability through existing supply chains. Thus, this study highlights both practical and theoretical implications for the specific route and environment as it brings out challenges and opportunities for low carbon future in realistic aspects.

However, the analysis identified uncertainties that should be addressed in future research. Fully electric island ferries show promise for the studied Estonian route due to low operating costs and emissions. The economic analysis should be expanded to compare investment needs for port-side and onboard systems, and to include sensitivity analyses on key parameters such as electricity and fuel prices. Furthermore, the studied ferry operates in regions partially covered by ice, posing challenges for fully electric operation. Based on the infeasibility shown by the conducted simulations, it remains uncertain whether fully electric vessels can maintain the current schedules under continuous rough weather conditions, highlighting the importance of hybrid system availability. Improving energy consumption estimates under such conditions will require the integration of weather information, e.g., wind and wave conditions, and physics-based simulations.

From the GHG emissions perspective, the fully electric configuration resulted in a 47% reduction in WtW GHG emissions compared to diesel when using current grid electricity. A significantly greater reduction, up to 96%, is achievable under scenarios assuming low-emission electricity. These results underscore both the importance of electricity sourcing and the shortcomings in current GHG assessment guidelines, which vary by country and lack consistency. Electricity generation methods vary widely across EU countries, many of which do not yet rely on fully renewable sources. Consequently, fully electric or diesel-electric hybrid ships operating in different countries may exhibit high WtW GHG emissions despite using the same technologies. This highlights a critical shortcoming in the current guidelines and underscores the need for further development by regulatory bodies such as the IMO and FuelEU Maritime to standardize the evaluation of GHG emissions for fully electric ships.

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REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission The European Green Deal Available online: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [2] Ministry of Climate National Energy and Climate Plan Available online: <https://kliimaministerium.ee/en/national-energy-and-climate-plan> (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [3] European Commission Decarbonising Maritime Transport – FuelEU Maritime Available online: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/maritime/decarbonising-maritime-transport-fueleu-maritime_en (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [4] Armstrong, J. Climate Impacts of Exemptions to EU’s Shipping Proposals; 2022;
- [5] Eea; Emsa EMTER 2025., doi:10.2800/3162144.
- [6] Statistics Estonia Population Available online: <https://stat.ee/en/find-statistics/statistics-theme/population> (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [7] Association of Estonian Towns and Municipalities Population in Local Municipalities Available online: <https://www.elvl.ee/elanike-arv> (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [8] OpenStreetMap OpenStreetMap Available online: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>.
- [9] ENTSO-E ENTSO-E Transparency Platform Available online: <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>.
- [10] Nordic-Baltic Hydrogen Corridor Available online: <https://sites.google.com/view/nordic-baltic-hydrogen-corridor/english> (accessed on 12 May 2025).
- [11] Otsason, R.; Laasma, A.; Gülmez, Y.; Kotta, J.; Tapaninen, U. Comparative Analysis of the Alternative Energy: Case of Reducing GHG Emissions of Estonian Pilot Fleet. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 2025, Vol. 13, Page 305 2025, 13, 305, doi:10.3390/JMSE13020305.
- [12] European Commission 2023 Biomethane Country Fiches Available online: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/2023-biomethane-country-fiches_en (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [13] Põllumajandusudised Riik Suunab Biometaani Tootmise Suurendamise Ligi 20 Miljonit Eurot Available online: <https://www.pollumajandus.ee/uudised/2024/05/30/riik-suunab-biometaani-tootmise-suurendamise-ligi-20-miljonit-eurot> (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [14] ThoriTanklad Eesti Available online: <https://en.thoritanklad.ee/> (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [15] Spire Maritime Maritime AIS Data for Vessel Tracking. 2025.
- [16] Estonian Safety Investigation Bureau Final Report of the Safety Investigation: Case Number M210721; 2024;
- [17] Di Ilio, G.; Bionda, A.; Ponzini, R.; Salvatore, F.; Cigolotti, V.; Minutillo, M.; Georgopoulou, C.; Mahos, K. Towards the Design of a Hydrogen-Powered Ferry for Cleaner Passenger Transport. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2024, doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.08.434.
- [18] Chatzinikolaou, S.; Ventikos, N. Applications of Life Cycle Assessment in Shipping Available online: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280313533_Applications_of_Life_Cycle_Assessment_in_Shipping (accessed on 7 May 2025).
- [19] European Commission FuelEU Maritime Initiative: Council Adopts New Law to Decarbonise the Maritime Sector - Consilium Available online: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/07/25/fueleu-maritime-initiative-council-adopts-new-law-to-decarbonise-the-maritime-sector/> (accessed on 9 May 2025).
- [20] IMO 2024 Guidelines on Life Cycle GHG Intensity of Marine Fuels; 2024;
- [21] Eurostat Shedding Light on Energy in Europe – 2024 Edition - Interactive Publications Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/energy-2024> (accessed on 7 May 2025).

- [22] Gopujkar, S.; Worm, J. Assessing the Benefits of Electrification for the Mackinac Island Ferry from an Environmental and Economic Perspective. *Sustainability* 2024, Vol. 16, Page 4297 2024, 16, 4297, doi:10.3390/SU16104297.
- [23] Nowtricity Current Emissions in Estonia Available online: <https://www.nowtricity.com/country/estonia/>.
- [24] Otsason, R.; Tapaninen, U. Decarbonizing City Water Traffic: Case of Comparing Electric and Diesel-Powered Ferries. *Sustainability* 2023, Vol. 15, Page 16170 2023, 15, 16170, doi:10.3390/SU152316170.
- [25] Feng, Y.; Dai, L.; Yue, M.; Hu, H.; Fang, S. Assessing the Decarbonization Potential of Electric Ships for Inland Waterway Freight Transportation. *Transp Res D Transp Environ* 2024, 129, 104151, doi:10.1016/J.TRD.2024.104151.
- [26] Chang, C.C.; Huang, M.L.; Li, C.H. Analysis of Emission Reduction Strategies for the Use of Alternative Fuels and Natural Carbon Sinks in International Bulk Shipping. *Energy Conversion and Management: X* 2024, 24, 100702, doi:10.1016/J.ECMX.2024.100702.
- [27] Fingrid Real-Time CO2 Emissions Estimate Available online: <https://www.fingrid.fi/en/electricity-market-information/real-time-co2-emissions-estimate/>.
- [28] Hart, W.E.; Watson, J.P.; Woodruff, D.L. Pyomo: Modeling and Solving Mathematical Programs in Python. In *Proceedings of the Mathematical Programming Computation*; 2011; Vol. 3, pp. 219–260.
- [29] Forrest, John; Ralphs, Ted; Vigerske, Stefan; Gambini Santos, Haroldo; Hafer, Lou; Kristjansson, Bjarni, et al. *Coin-or/Cbc.*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.2720283.
- [30] Ammenberg, C.; Gustafsson, J.; O'shea, M.; Gray, R.; Lyng, N.; Eklund, K.-A.; Murphy, M.D. Perspectives on Biomethane as a Transport Fuel within a Circular Economy, Energy, and Environmental System; 2021; Vol. 37; ISBN 978-1-910154-95-3.
- [31] Guan, W.; Chen, L.; Wang, Z.; Chen, J.; Ye, Q.; Fan, H. A 500 KW Hydrogen Fuel Cell-Powered Vessel: From Concept to Sailing. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2024, 89, 1466–1481, doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.09.418.
- [32] Mojarrad, M.; Thorne, R.J.; Rødseth, K.L. Technical and Cost Analysis of Zero-Emission High-Speed Ferries: Retrofitting from Diesel to Green Hydrogen. *Heliyon* 2024, 10, doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e27479.
- EUR-Lex Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/1184 Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02023R1184-20240610> (accessed on 9 May 2025).